

FORMING STUDENTS' CREATIVE ACTIVITY THROUGH DIDACTIC GAMES IN THE PRIMARY CLASS

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Abstract. *It is very important to form creative activities in primary school students. With this, they will be able to form independent work skills in future practical processes. Therefore, in the article, the importance was given to the formation of creative activities of elementary school students by means of didactic games.*

Keywords: *mother tongue and reading literacy, creativity, purpose of education, teacher-student cooperation, creative potential, advanced technologies.*

Education is a cooperative activity of teachers and students, and in this process, the development of a person, his education and upbringing is also realized. In the lessons, the teacher conveys his knowledge, skills and abilities to students through exercises, and students acquire the ability to use them as a result of mastering them. In the process of learning, students use different forms of learning, that is, they rely on specific differences in receiving, processing and applying the information being learned. In the course of education, issues of education and upbringing are solved in the form of cooperation between teachers and students during classes, independent work of students, extracurricular activities.

The purpose of education is formed in accordance with the needs of society. Therefore, the goal of education should be appropriate and proportionate. The goal of education in scientific literature is to create skills and competencies, develop logical-creative thinking, improve communicative literacy, inculcate the national idea, form oriental education, define personality it is emphasized that it consists of spiritual enrichment. Based on the educational goal, students' communication culture is improved by increasing their independent thinking, oral and written literacy, and developing logical thinking. On the basis of the educational goal, spiritual, ideological and sophisticated education is given. In the process of language learning, there is an opportunity to get closer to the cultural and moral values of the people.

It is known that the application of advanced pedagogy and new information technologies in education not only increases the effectiveness of training sessions, but also creates an independent and logically thinking, well-rounded, highly moral person by applying the achievements of science in practice. plays an important role in education.

In today's era of increasing civilization, every society needs creative people. This is natural. Because the changes taking place in the world every minute require this.

Creativity is an individual characteristic of a person, the use and development of cultural tools based on personal concepts. Creativity is an important pedagogical problem that is analyzed from a psychological point of view and requires research from a pedagogical point of view.

Creativity is a pedagogical category that encourages students to be innovative. Creativity is the integration of students' personal qualities. Because if the student is not curious and aspiring by nature, such a student will never be able to show creativity. The creative potential of the student is formed and creative abilities are developed when overcoming the problems encountered during the student's independent implementation of various problems.

The concept of creative potential is complex and diverse. Creativity is not a quality that emerges in students by itself, it is a student's ability to overcome difficulties in the process of striving for new things, mastering new things and applying them in his daily activities, using innovative new things in his work. It is related to being able to use it actively and creatively. The formation of the student's creativity comes from "needs, directions and concepts of "I". Dialogue serves as the main pragmatic description of the development of creativity in the breadth of learning. Psychologists have tried to analyze the creativity of the individual in the process of students writing essays, quickly responding to various assignments in the course of the lesson, and looking at their educational assignments based on didactic games with a new approach.

It should be noted that the interest in using interactive methods and information technologies in the educational process is increasing day by day. One of the reasons for this is that until now, in traditional education, students were taught only to acquire ready-made knowledge, and the use of modern technologies allows them to search for the knowledge they acquire, independent study and thinking, analysis. even teaches them to draw their own conclusions. In this process, the teacher creates conditions for the development, formation, learning and upbringing of the individual, and at the same time, he also performs the functions of management and guidance. Today, in education "Brainstorming", "Thoughtstorming", "Networks" method, "Sinquain", "BBB", "Fifth plus", "6x6x6", "Debate", "Role-playing game", We know very well the active use of modern technologies such as FSMU, "Working in small groups", "Rounded snow", "Zigzag", "I will say the last word". However, at the same time, didactic games do not remain active in the course of the lesson.

In primary education, the game is a form of creative activity. In this, the student develops emotionally, emotionally, intellectually and morally on the basis of knowledge and understanding of social and material existence. That is why it is necessary to pay attention to the use of didactic games in primary education or, in particular, in the teaching processes organized within the framework of the subject of mother tongue and reading literacy. After all, with this, it is possible to get rid of the features of getting bored and avoiding the lesson in a student of junior school age.

A number of research works have been conducted in psychology, ethnography, culture, and pedagogy about games and their role in human development. At the end of the 19th century, the German scientist K. Gross tried to systematically study didactic games, while the German psychologist K. Bühler studied didactic games as a "satisfying" activity. According to L.S. Vygotsky and A.N. Leontiev, they theoretically connected and studied didactic games with their social nature and focus on certain activities, while D.B. Elkonin defines the management of personal behavior and interprets it as an improving activity. . But the only and most important main feature of didactic games is its importance in education.

In the didactic games that are used or can be used in primary school mother tongue and reading literacy classes, the child's behavior is freely formed and socialized. The most important aspect of didactic games is its dual nature, and its compatibility with dramatic art. On the one hand, if the participants of the didactic game perform real activities related to certain non-standard tasks during its implementation, on the other hand, the games acquire a conditional character, deviating from real situations, feeling responsible for most of these activities. Therefore, the dual function of didactic games is the reason why it has a developing result. Elements of didactic games or game activities are widely used in the educational process. They are in the form of business games, didactic games, role-playing games, computer games, etc.

Didactic games fulfill educational goals and are adapted to them. For the first time, F. Fribil and M. Montessori developed the teaching tasks for the use of the system of didactic games in the field of preschool education, and O. Dikroli conducted research for primary education. From the 60s and 70s, it began to be used not only in primary education, but also in general secondary education. In the 80s, especially, business games began to spread widely. The main feature of business games is that the game plan is oriented towards the educational goal. Because the educational goal is solved within the framework of game tasks.

In conclusion, it should be said that during the educational process, students acquire the skills of identifying, analyzing and making independent decisions when performing tasks of a creative nature. They get acquainted with the methods of preparing visual aids, solving problems that require research in scientific description. Today, the learner is required to act actively, make independent decisions, and quickly adapt to the changing conditions of life. For this, the learner should acquire the necessary knowledge independently and apply it in practice; offer visions aimed at solving problems, identify and solve new problems; free and independent thinking; to have the ability to create innovative ideas; he should have skills and qualifications such as independent work on the development of his intellectual potential. At the same time, it gives a positive result if it is used in lessons to repeat games and tasks or in reinforcement lessons. The choice of which type of game-task depends on the type of lesson, the level of training of students to perform games-tasks, their level of knowledge, opportunities for independent creative work, the ability to quickly restore what they have learned in memory, and the degree to which creativity is formed. should be Not forgetting these aspects, it is necessary to implement the work of encouraging students to be creative at the first stage of education - from primary education. It can be said that the use of didactic games is also effective.

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